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EVALUATION OF THE READING SPEED OF NEAR VISUAL ACUITY AFTER PROVIDING LOW VISION INTERVENTION

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ABSTRACT**BACKGROUND:**

The prevalence of low vision has been increased overtime. So many different types of low vision devices were developed within few years. From so many studies, it has been proved that low vision rehabilitation is the better option for low vision patients to improve their quality of life. Low vision rehabilitation will improve quality of life of patients by enhancing their residual vision for distance as well as for near activities. Reading speed for near activities is also an important part for development of reading ability, their confidence and their performance. So, in this study, reading speed will be measured with the help of MN Read chart (continuous text chart) and thereby evaluate improvement in reading speed after providing low vision devices for near.

METHOD:

This study is cross sectional in which 102 Patients were enrolled in the study visited at Shri C. H. Nagri Municipal Eye hospital (Tertiary eye care center). All patients were undergoing a standardized ophthalmological examination. Best corrected visual acuity for distance and near has been assessed. Starting point of magnification required for low vision patients has been calculated and was finalized according to their visual ability, needs and demands, occupation and affordability. Then, according to needs of Low Vision Patients, Low Vision Intervention has been given with proper training and finally Reading Speed being measured with final recommended Low Vision Aid. After provision of low vision aids, reading speed is evaluated using standardized MN Read text chart. Reading speed has been measured according to Word per Minute formula.

RESULTS:

102 low vision patients were enrolled in the study, who visited tertiary eye care center, among which 53.92% were male population and 46.08% were female population. Mean Reading speed was 43.82 ± 24.73 wpm after provision of low vision aids for the whole group. Three major causes were found more common; Chorio-Retinal Coloboma (22.54%), Retinal detachment (15.68%) and Retinitis Pigmentosa (13.72%). The management of all low Vision patients was found to be different for distance and near according to the patients Visual Acuity, needs and affordability.

CONCLUSION:

This indicates the great value of low vision rehabilitation through adequate providing of low vision aids for the improvement of reading ability. Low vision Intervention will help patient to maintain and regain their reading ability, which can lead to an increase in independency, mental ability, confidence and quality of life.

KEYWORD: near visual acuity, low vision intervention, intervention

INTRODUCTION

Low vision was originally defined by world health organization (WHO) as “A person with low vision is one who has impairment of visual functioning even after treatment and/or standard refractive correction, and has a visual acuity of less than 6/18 to light perception, or a visual

field of less than 10 degrees from the point of fixation, but who uses, or is potentially able to use, vision for planning and/or execution of a task.”¹

The rehabilitation of visually impaired individual may involve a variety of treatment modalities including prescription, eyewear optical devices, electronic aids adaptive computer software, glare control modification of patient’s environment counseling and education skill of patient and family training, independent living aids, occupational therapy, mental health intervention orientation and mobility training and driving rehabilitation.²

Table 1: Common causes of blindness and low vision in various regions of world³

Africa	America and Canada	East med. And Asia specific	Europe	Oceania
Senile cataract		Cataract		
Glaucoma			Age Related Macular Degeneration	
Corneal opacity (trachomatous and non-trachomatous)		corneal opacity (non- trachomatous)		
Uncorrected aphakia		Infections (Trachomatous and non- trachomatous)	Glaucoma	Age Related Macular Degeneration
Infections and diseases (Onchocerciasis, trachomatous and non trachomatous)	Diabetic Retinopathy	Retinitis Pigmentosa	Cataract	Diabetic retinopathy
Xerophthalmia	Cataract	Age Related Macular Degeneration	Diabetic retinopathy	Diabetic retinopathy
Trauma	Age Related Macular Degeneration	Diabetic Retinopathy	Hereditary Retinal dystrophy	Cataract
Macular degeneration		Glaucoma	Optic atrophy	
		Optic atrophy		

Magnification:

It is the ratio of the size of the image to the size of the object.

Methods of Determining the Appropriate Near Magnification:

Several methods can be used to determine the amount of magnification or equivalent power for near:

1. Lebensohn’s “reciprocal of vision” rule calculates the needed magnification by using the patient’s best corrected distance acuity and a near target acuity. By dividing the denominator of the distance Snellen fraction by the denominator of the near Snellen fraction of the estimated target acuity, the required magnification is obtained. To convert the resultant magnification to diopters, the magnification number can be multiplied by 4.

2. Kestenbaum's rule also uses distance acuity to predict near magnification. Using the Snellen fraction of best corrected distance acuity, the denominator is divided by the numerator to obtain the dioptric power needed to achieve 1M or 20/50 reduced Snellen.
3. Near magnification can also be determined by using a simple ratio comparing near VA to a target acuity. This method involves the following steps:
 - a. The patient's best near acuity (BNA) is determined with a single character acuity card and the testing distance (TD) is recorded.
 - b. A target near acuity (TNA) is determined and a ratio is set up ($BNA/TNA=TD/?$).
 - c. The unknown number (?) is the new reading distance that the reading material must be brought to obtain the appropriate magnification
 - d. The reciprocal of this new reading distance (?) will provide the practitioner with the power of the lens required to read the target acuity.⁵

Reading speed: It is an objective measure of reading performance. Research has shown that patients (with either normal or low vision) often require letters that are two or three times larger than their acuity limits before they can achieve their maximum reading speeds. The ***MNREAD ACUITY CHARTS*** can be used to measure reading speed at different print sizes, and hence, can be used to determine the print size which supports the patient's maximum reading speed.

Calculation of reading speed

Reading speed is measured in **words per minute**. With the ***MNREAD ACUITY CHARTS*** the reading speed calculation is simplified because each sentence has the same length: 10 standard length words. Reading speed is given by: $\text{reading speed} = 60 \times (10 - \text{errors}) / (\text{time in seconds})$ Error = words that were missed or read incorrectly⁶

Low Vision Management: Three types of low vision aids were prescribed

- A. OPTICAL DEVICES
- B. NON-OPTICAL DEVICES
- C. COMPUTER ASSISSTIVE DEVICES

Table:2 Shows Low Vision Aids

OPTICAL DEVICES	NON-OPTICAL DEVICES	COMPUTER ASSISSTIVE DEVICES
<p>For Distance: Monocular and binocular telescopes, Binocular Telescope, Spectacle Mounted Telescope</p> <p>for Nearby: Spectacle magnifier, Stand magnifier, Bar magnifier, Dome magnifier, Hand held magnifier, Cut way stand magnifier, Illuminated stand magnifier</p>	<p>Large print books, Bold line notebook, Felt tip pen, Reading lamp, Reading stand, Talking clock, Signature guide, Peaked caps, Filters, Tinted lenses, Torch</p>	<p>Closed –Circuit Television (CCTV), Head-Mounted Devices (HMD) Low Vision enhancement System (LVES) V-Max</p>

Importance of Reading speed: Speed reading is a useful and valuable skill which can save your time. Through speed reading a better understanding of any argument or discussion can be possibly done which can ultimately help in benefiting your work and career as because through speed reading a “clear and bigger” picture understanding can be done speedily.⁷

Purpose of this study:

Reading Speed is an important skill for Low Vision Patient to boost up their Confidence, reading ability and independency for performing near tasks with the help of Low Vision Aids. So, the purpose of this study is to find out the Reading speed after providing LVA by keeping in mind cause and need of low vision patient.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY: MATERIALS:

1. Torch
2. Retinoscope
3. Trial set
4. Log MAR visual acuity chart for distance
5. MN Read chart for near
6. Peli-Robson contrast sensitivity chart
7. D-15 color vision test
8. Low vision kit

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- † Low vision patients according to WHO criteria.
- † Age Group 11-90 years
- † Patients who are compatible with English language.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- † Patients who are totally blind or having no perception of light in both eye
- † One eyed patient
- † Intellectually Disabled Persons
- † Illiterate Patients

METHODS: 102 low Vision patients were enrolled after informed consent was obtained. They underwent a comprehensive eye examination and a step wise approach was followed for each and every patient. Following steps were included for thorough eye examination: Demographic data were taken which includes age, gender and detail history of patients. Like ocular history, family history, functional, occupational and vocational history. Visual acuity, Objective and Subjective refraction, color vision, contrast sensitivity, visual field were assessed. After the provision of LVA, Reading Speed is evaluated using MN Read chart. Distance visual acuity was assessed with Log MAR chart. Near visual acuity was assessed with MN Read chart. Objective refraction was performed using Retinoscope. Subjective refraction was performed using trial frame, full aperture trial lenses and vision charts. Color vision were assessed in each and every patient using panel D- 15 color vision test monocularly as well as binocularly. Contrast sensitivity were assessed using Peli Robson Contrast Sensitivity chart Monocularly at 1 m distance. Visual field were assessed using Amsler grid, Confrontation test and/or Perimetry according to their visual field loss. Low vision devices trials were prescribed given to the patient accordingly as per patient's need. Starting point of ADD has been evaluated with the help of Kestenbaum's Rule as it gives approximate Magnification within lesser time as compared to EVP (Equivalent Power). Reading speed were assessed using MN Read Chart after Providing Low Vision Aid. Stop watch was used to record the time taken to read one sentence. Reading Speed= $60 \times (10 - \text{errors}) / \text{time in seconds}$.

RESULTS:

102 low vision patients meet the eligibility criteria were included in this study. Among these, 55(53.92%) were male patients and 47 (46.08%) were female patients.

Graph-1:
of Male patients included
GENDER
Male
Female

Shows Ratio and Female who were in the study RATIO

Graph -2:

of age distribution of patients
Age Distribution

Shows Ratio

- † The age of low vision patients which were included in this study was between 11 to 90 years with mean age was 41.72(±24.05) years.
- † Among these, highest number of low vision patients was found in age group between 11 to 20 years. This shows that younger patients were more affected with low vision. They require more Reading Speed for their work to get benefit in their career.

Table -3: Causes of low vision

Causes of low vision	Number of Eyes	Percentage
Chorio Retinal Coloboma	46	22.54%
Retinal Detachment	26	12.74%
Retinitis Pigmentosa	30	14.70%
Diabetic Retinopathy	21	10.29%
Hypertension	12	5.88%
Corneal Degeneration	8	3.92%
Nystagmus	10	4.90%
Macular Scar	9	4.41%
Optic Atrophy	6	2.94%
Glaucoma	6	2.94%
Central Retinal Artery Occlusion	4	1.96%
Foveal Hypoplasia	4	1.96%

Macular Dystrophy	4	1.96%
Corneal Opacity	5	2.45%
Macular Hole	3	1.47%
Myopic Degeneration	2	0.98%
Age Related Macular Degeneration	2	0.98%
Diabetic Maculopathy	2	0.98%
Peripheral Neuropathy	2	0.98%
Lattice Degeneration	2	0.98%

Chorio Retinal Coloboma (22.54%), Retinitis Pigmentosa (14.70%) and Retinal Detachment (12.74%) were found to be most commonest causes of Low Vision.

Graph-3: Shows distribution of patients according to refractive error
Distribution according to Refractive Error

Out of 102 patients (204 eyes), Astigmatism (128 eyes) was found to be the highest in all type of refractive error.

Graph-4: Shows distribution of patients according to category of visual loss
Category of visual loss

From this graph, it is clear that central field loss (47.05%) is the most common type of visual loss as compared to peripheral field loss and overall blur vision.

Graph-5: Shows distribution of patients according to low vision devices prescribed for distance

This graph shows the distribution of low vision devices recommended for distance. As, for distance low vision devices, Telescope is the only best option for distance/ spot purpose. Whereas, from this graph, it has been seen that majority of the patients (70.58%) are fine with their residual vision for distance.

Graph-6: Shows distribution of patients according to low vision devices prescribed for near

Graph :7 Shows Reading Speed according to Low Vision Causes

Low Vision Patients with Diabetic Retinopathy (71.22%) shows maximum Reading Speed whereas all Macular related disorders like Age Related Macular Degeneration (20%), Diabetic Maculopathy (31%), Macular Hole (28.82%), Macular Dystrophy (46.5%) shows reduced Reading Speed.

DISCUSSION:

Visual impairment caused by uncorrected refractive error is defined as visual acuity of 6/18 to perception of light (PL) in the best Seeing Eye or a visual field less than 10 degrees from point of fixation. It is necessary to point out that reading speed is an important parameter for evaluating the results of rehabilitation in patients with visual impairment, because reading is much more demanding than identifying a single letter in the visual acuity test. Reading impairment has been found to be the most common complaint among low vision patients attending focus groups in quality-of-life investigation settings.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ Reading ability is not only an important function in daily living tasks but also a complex psychophysical measure, including two related dimensions, reading speed (RS) and reading acuity (RA).¹⁷ Reading ability is not routinely measured during most clinical examinations; nonetheless, detecting people with reading disability is important so that clinicians can refer these patients to low vision services. Visual acuity (VA), as the worldwide standard measure of vision function, is a simple criterion for assessing the need for referral, but reduced VA predicts only in part the level of reading impairment in low vision people and, particularly, has a poor correlation with RS.¹⁸ Reading speed has been measured with MNREAD ACUITY chart. In this chart, each sentence contains 60 characters (including a space between each word and at the end of each line). The vocabulary used in the sentences is selected from words appearing with high frequency in 2nd and 3rd grade reading material.³ **Nhung Xuan Nguyen et al** conducted a study on different stages of age-related macular degeneration (AMD) and found that reading speed was increased to 72 ± 35 after the provision of low vision aids. This study also found improvement of Reading Speed after provision of Low Vision Aids which correlates with the above study. **Stephen G. Whittaker et al** found that there are four different visual factors that significantly affect reading rates. Acuity reserve, Contrast reserve, Field of view, In case of

maculopathy, central scotoma size. This study also found that Reading Ability significantly reduced with Macular related disorders. According to other study done by **GE Legge et al**, found that Age-related maculopathy predicted slower Reading speed than other causes of central field loss, which correlates with the present study, where Age Related Macular Degeneration has least Reading Speed (20 wpm). According to present study, the major causes of low vision were found Chorio-Retinal Coloboma, Retinal Detachment, Retinitis Pigmentosa and Diabetic Retinopathy and Mean Reading speed was 43.82 ± 24.73 wpm after providing Low Vision Intervention. Present study shows that Reading Speed of younger patient was more Reduced as compared to older age group. This may be due to the cause of low vision with respect to number of Low Vision Patients included in this study. In this younger age group (1130years) Chorio-Retinal Coloboma was the major cause for Low Vision, which damages the Macular and Choroidal part of Eyes and there by reduces the Reading Ability. So, it is important for those patients to intervene Low Vision Rehabilitation within proper time and phase to protect or prevent their future life significant events and/or independency with regards to Activities of Daily Livings and leisure activities. The common causes of Low Vision were Chorio-Retinal Coloboma, Retinal Detachment and Retinitis Pigmentosa having Reading Speed 30.48, 52.86 and 36.68 wpm respectively. But, Reading Speed was highest in Diabetic Retinopathy and lowest in Age Related Macular Degeneration. As, in Age Related Macular Degeneration, Macular area is affected, the Reading Ability is more deprived which indirectly Reduces Reading Speed of patients. From this study, it has been seen that not only in Age Related Macular Degeneration, but all Macular related disorders have low Reading Speed and these causes are more common in age group between 11 to 40 years. This age group suffers already from different significant life events, with having Low Reading Ability will make them more depressed, if Low Vision Rehabilitation has not been given in proper time and phase. From present study, Low Vision Devices has been recommended for distance and near to all Low Vision patients whereas, Low Vision Devices for distance has not been accepted easily by Low Vision patients (70.58%) from the present study, it has been proved that Low Vision Rehabilitation for Near has been given more value as compared to distance Low Vision Devices, which indirectly shows that the Reading Ability has make Low Vision patients more handicap than distance tasks. So, to find out Reading Speed of Low Vision patients with Recommended Low Vision Devices has been given more importance to improve their Vocational, Recreational and Educational activities. An important aspect of present study is to show the great benefit of providing low vision aids for the improvement of reading ability. This study also shows the distribution of category of vision loss, in which, it has been found that, central field loss was the major type of visual loss as compared to peripheral field loss and overall blur vision. Additionally, management of all different types of low vision patients with different Low Vision Causes should be performed properly in a right time to make the betterment for the low vision patients.

CONCLUSION

This importance of low vision rehabilitation through adequate provision of low vision aids will increase the reading ability and lifestyle of low vision patients. Among all 102 low vision patients, Astigmatism was seen highest in number and Chorio Retinal Coloboma, Retinal detachment, Retinitis Pigmentosa were the commonest low vision causes respectively. It has been concluded that central field loss was seen more compared to peripheral field loss and overall blur vision. Reading Speed is seen highest in Diabetic Retinopathy and lowest in Age Related Macular Degeneration. Low vision Intervention will help patient to maintain and regain their reading ability, which can lead to an increase in independence, communication, mental agility and quality of life. So, as an Optometrist, it is always helpful to remember five factors in their mind while assessing and managing low vision patients, i.e., social, financial, economic, psychological and visual factors.

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